

Research

The influence of service quality and innovation on customer satisfaction in Electricidade de Timor-Leste (EDTL)

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Abstract: *Electricidade de Timor-Leste (EDTL) is a state-owned enterprise which is located in Timor-Leste and engaged in the supply and distribution of electricity for the industrial and household sectors. EDTL was established in 2003 under the Decree-Law No. 13/2003 – Bases of the National Electricity. EDTL ensures the satisfaction of the basic electricity supply needs for the whole populations, but also for the public and private entities in various sectors of activity through the creation of conditions conducive to the development of each services. Throughout 2019, there were many complains about the supply instability that was supplied by EDTL. which is usually caused by the weather. So that, during the rainy season complain always increases compared to the dry season. The EDTL continues to improve and innovate its services in order to satisfy their customers. From that, this study has “The influence of service quality and innovation on customer satisfaction in Electricidade de Timor-Leste (EDTL)” as a title. Hence, this study is done in order to analyze the customer assessments regarding the quality of service and innovation of Electricidade de Timor-Leste on customer satisfaction; analyze the simultaneous influence of service quality and innovation on customer satisfaction; analyze the partial influence of service quality on customer satisfaction; and as well analyze the partial influence of innovation on customer satisfaction. This study uses 100 respondents who are all EDTL customers with household customer criteria. Some analysis was also done such as descriptive analysis method; validity and reliability test; classical assumption test, F test, and T test. The result showed that the descriptive analysis test of service quality, innovation and customer satisfaction are good; all items are valid and reliable; the classical assumption test are good; from the F test, we can conclude that service quality and innovation influence simultaneously the customer satisfaction; and from the T test, we can conclude that service quality influences partially the customer satisfaction, and innovation influences partially the customer satisfaction.*

Keywords: *services quality, innovation, customer satisfaction*

I- Introduction

Business competition is getting tougher and it forces business people to keep making change periodically and abreast of development in the business world, especially in the service sector. It

pushes the provider of services to become more creative, and especially to design a strategy for service which is more specific and can be implemented in the business world. It can be done by increasing the quality of the service in order to achieve the company's goals, because the company's success is measured through customer satisfaction. Customers are company assets that must be taken into account maximally such as maintaining and caring for other company assets (Jauman, 2018).

Service quality is an activity carried out by the company on a regular basis and continues to improve service. The goal is to maintain a good relationship between the company and customers, and also make the customers feel safe and comfortable with the company, because customer comfort is crucial for the company success. It means that customers are the main income of companies, and improving service quality means important support from the human resources especially the one who is working on customer service because they are our frontline (Rusydi, 2017).

Eletricidade de Timor-Leste (EDTL) is a state-owned enterprise of Timor-Leste that is engaged in the supply and distribution of electricity for the industrial and household sectors. Although, Eletricidade de Timor-Leste (EDTL) is a state-owned enterprise it is very important to improve the Service quality to customers throughout Timor-Leste. One of the quality services provided by EDTL is to provide education and detailed explanation to customers about the procedures of using electricity as do other service sectors. As we know, currently electricity is an important part of either our daily or professional life so that the satisfaction of the customer is important. state electricity company has new product innovation, in the form of prepaid electricity, is the latest service from state electricity company with various advantages in regulating the use of electrical energy through prepaid electronic meters. This latest innovation is created in order to give more convenience to the customer in order to increase their appreciation towards the state electricity company. Thanks to this innovation, customer is freer in controlling their electricity usage according to their needs and desires. In addition, the use of electricity becomes more convenient and more controlled (Markoni, 2015)

Private enterprises and state-owned enterprises must continue to innovate in order to pursue technological development in the era of globalization. Innovation is not just about the benefits of initiating change and latest update in the process of change, but especially service innovation is a process that starts from the discovery of a concept or is a development of the service itself (Aouad & sahar, 2019).

The purpose of this research is to analyze the customer assessments regarding the quality of service, innovation of Electricidade de Timor-Leste and customer satisfaction; analyze the simultaneous influence of service quality and innovation on customer satisfaction; analyze the partial influence of service quality on customer satisfaction; and as well analyze the partial influence of innovation on customer satisfaction.

II- Literature Review

2.1 Service Quality

Service quality provided by a company can affect customer satisfaction and also build a strong bond between the two parties in the long term (Han and Yeh, 2017). Customer satisfaction is the result received by customers when the service that they have experienced exceeds their expectations. In marketing, it is seen as a global evaluation of service experience from time to time (Dawi, 2018). Service quality in each company affects customer satisfaction, because each customer expects a maximum satisfaction from the product or service provided by the company. Services are considered good if perceptions exceed expectations, it will be considered good or adequate if only equivalent to service expectations and will be considered bad or less if not in accordance with customer expectations (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017). There is five specific dimensions of service quality that applied in various service contexts, each dimension has its own indicators such as *tangible* which is covering physical facilities, equipment, employees and means of communication; *reliability* which is including the ability to perform services that are promised reliably and accurately; *responsiveness* which is including the desire of staff to help customers and provide services with responses; *assurance* which is including knowledge and politeness of employees, as well as the capabilities of the staff, free from danger and risk; and finally *empathy* which is including the ease of relationships, good communication, personal attention, and understanding the needs of customers (Zeithaml & Berry, 2016).

2.2 Innovation

Service innovation is a differentiator between the latest and the previous product that created by a company in order to make it better. Based on the existing concept, innovation is something different from previous products because there is a system development (Durst, 2015). Innovative is a combination of the overall achievement of an organization as a result of renewal and

improvement efforts made by considering various aspects of an organization's innovation, because innovation is one of the very important steps to always develop and will affect marketing performance. An innovative performance is a form of corporate collaboration to introduce a new creation to achieve certain goals (Tuan, 2016). Product innovation is the introduction and development of new types of goods or services that are different from previous inventions and complement the shortcomings of previous inventions with more emphasis on quality strategies. Innovation is a tactic taken by the company to develop and perfecting existing products in order to achieve a certain quality to satisfy customers (Atalay et al., 2013). Innovation is a development and labor that is carried out by a company. With innovation, it can retain existing customers, so the company really does a good development strategy (Haji, 2017). The performance of a service innovation can have various aspects and predecessors. Service innovation performance is defined as the extent to which companies achieve competitive advantage and commercial advantage associated with service innovation (Mennens et al., 2018; Storey et al., 2016). Innovation is a stage that starts from the planning, process, manufacture, development, and implementation of the company where this is something new for the company and customers. Based on the existing concept explains that innovation is a system development, with the aim of making it easier for customers and companies to access information and others (Goudarz, 2017).

2.3 Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is one of the main factors needed between the company and customers in the long term. Talking about satisfaction or dissatisfaction, consists of talking about feelings of pleasure or disappointment that comes from the comparison between the performance of a product of personal desires (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017). Customer satisfaction is the expectation or feeling of someone for the purchase of an item or service. If consumers are dissatisfied, the company looks for a method to overcome consumer complaints and problems that occur, consumer complains is a positive information for the company because the information can help companies to continue to improve their Service quality or products (Cashmere, 2017). Satisfaction is a function of impression of performance and expectations, the impression of performance as follows: if the performance is below expectations, then the customer feels not satisfied, if the performance meets expectations, the customer will feel satisfied, if the performance exceeds expectations, the customer will feel very satisfied (Irwan, 2012).

III- Research Framework and Hypothesis Development

Customer satisfaction is a feedback in the form of evaluation after purchasing a number of goods or services compared to customer expectations. Customer satisfaction is measured using customer expectations with the performance of goods or services that can meet customer needs and desires. Satisfied customers show that there is a similarity between the performance of goods and services with customer expectations, where it will encourage them to purchase again. At the same time, disappointed customers will persuade other customers not to purchase again and as a result, they will move to other brand competitors (Rakaza, 2016). According to this theory the third hypothesis for this research is “*H1: Service quality and innovation have a simultaneous influence on customer satisfaction*”

For customers, a service has a good quality when the company is able to resolve complains and also meet the customer needs in accordance with what is expected or exceeds expectations. Customer service will directly have an impact on customer satisfaction if the service provided has met customer expectations (Bolang, 2015). Service quality is the overall characteristics of a product or service in terms of the ability to meet predetermined or latent needs, with an emphasis on orienting the fulfilment of expectations to obtain a compatible use (Hiyadayati in Nguji, Tumbel, Rotinsulu, 2014). From this theory, the first hypothesis for this research is “*H2: Service quality has a partial influence on customer satisfaction*”.

Partially, the innovation has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction because the company is able to provide updates in the provision of services both from the technology used to serve consumers, improved interaction with consumers needed to maintain communication with consumers and the development of services provided to consumers (Aditi & Hermansyur, 2017). Service updates or system innovations affect customer satisfaction, with updates which can facilitate communication between companies and consumers, and it is also easy for companies to provide solutions about customer complains in a short time. (Rahman, 2019). According to this theory the second hypothesis for this research is “*H3: Innovation has a partial influence on customer satisfaction*”.

The research model for this study is as following

Figure 1: Research Model

IV- Methodology

The researcher uses a questionnaire to get the information related to study. The total of respondents is 100 persons. In this study, it is divided into four sections, the first section is related to the profile of Electricidade de Timor-Leste (EDTL) customers, the second section is regarding to the service quality, the third section is regarding to the innovation, and the last section is about the customer satisfaction. The independent variables are service quality and innovation, and the dependent variable is customer satisfaction. SPSS software was used in conducting all calculations and by doing some analysis such as validity and reliability test, normality test, multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test, and multiple linear regression test.

V- Results and Analysis

The validity test used Pearson Correlation by calculating the correlation between the values obtained from the questions. A question is said to be valid if the r_{count} level is greater than r_{table} and the significance value is below 0.05. The value of r of each questionnaire is positive and the value of $r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$ of these values can be concluded that all questions are valid, and these values can be seen in table 1.1 below.

Table 1 Validity test

Indicator	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	R-Table	Description
X1.1	29,3800	70,602	,685	0,1966	Valid
X1.2	29,7200	69,577	,689	0,1966	Valid
X1.3	29,8100	70,418	,660	0,1966	Valid
X1.4	29,8000	70,343	,704	0,1966	Valid
X1.5	29,4400	68,653	,820	0,1966	Valid
X1.6	29,9900	69,667	,684	0,1966	Valid
X1.7	29,8700	72,559	,592	0,1966	Valid
X1.8	29,3900	71,634	,675	0,1966	Valid
X1.9	29,5700	68,874	,757	0,1966	Valid
X1.10	29,5800	75,640	,508	0,1966	Valid
X2.1	6,620000	4,864	,506	0,1966	Valid
X2.2	6,440000	4,512	,589	0,1966	Valid
X2.3	6,560000	4,047	,513	0,1966	Valid
Y1	6,48000000	4,353	,779	0,1966	Valid
Y2	6,67000000	4,809	,662	0,1966	Valid
Y3	6,53000000	4,191	,675	0,1966	Valid

Source: Processed data

SPSS provides facilities to measure reliability with *Cronbach Alpha* statistical test. A variable is said to be reliable if it gives a *Cronbach Alpha* value > 0.70 . (Ghozali, 2013). Cronbach's alpha value of service quality is 0.912 which is greater than 0.70, Cronbach's alpha value of innovation is 0.713 which is also greater than 0.70, and Cronbach's alpha value of customer satisfaction is 0.839 which is as well greater than 0.70. From those result, we can conclude that the question that we have asked for service quality, innovation, and customer satisfaction are reliable. These results can be seen in table 2 below:

Table 2: Reliability test

No.	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Description
1	Service Quality (X1)	,912	Reliable
2	Innovation (X2)	,713	Reliable
3	Customer Satisfaction	,839	Reliable

Source: Processed data

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis is carried out to see each answer that each respondent gave to each question about service quality, innovation and customer satisfaction. The researcher conducted a descriptive analysis with the frequency distribution approach in order to see the level of service quality, innovation and customer satisfaction in EDTL.

The results showed that customers agreed to the quality of EDTL services with an actual score percentage value above 60 percent. This value shows that the ten (10) indicators are already in accordance with customer desires, but the indicator quickness in resolving problems is only 59.2 percent. This value shows that the EDTL service is not optimal, especially in term of quickness in resolving problems. These results can be seen in table 3 below.

Table 3: Actual score of service quality

Variable	Indicator	Actual Score
X1.1	Facilities	71,4
X1.2	Equipment	64,6
X1.3	Quickness in responding customers	62,8
X1.4	Staff's amiability	63
X1.5	Response to complains	60,2
X1.6	Quickness in resolving problems	59,2
X1.7	Staff's kindness	61,6
X1.8	Skills possessed by staffs	71,2
X1.9	Understanding customer's needs	67,6
X1.10	Good communication	67,4

Source: Processed data

Respondents' response to innovation shows us that the actual score percentage value is above 60%. This value indicates that the innovations in the curve by EDTL are good. The results can be seen in table 4 below.

Table 4: Actual Score of Innovation

Variable	Indicator	Actual Score
X2.1	Innovative service	63,8
X2.2	New technology development	67,4
X2.3	Interaction with new customers	65

Source: Processed data

Respondents' responses to customer satisfaction shows that the customers agree on EDTL service quality and innovation, with an actual score percentage value above 60%. This value indicates that the customer is satisfied with EDTL innovation. These results can be seen in table 5 below.

Table 5: Actual score of customer satisfaction

Variable	Indicator	Actual Score
Y1	Comfort felt by customers	67,2
Y2	EDTL service satisfaction	63,4
Y3	Early month bonus satisfaction	66,2

Source: Processed data

Normality test

Normality test aims to determine the distribution of variable that tested whether it is normally distributed or not, a good regression model possess a good distribution and normal or close to normal data distribution. (Ghozali, 2013). Detection method can be seen by spreading data points on the diagonal axis of the graph or looking at the histogram of the residuals. If the data spreads around the diagonal and follows the direction of the diagonal line or the histogram shows a normal distribution pattern, then it meets the normality assumption. The normality result shows that the data is normal and has met the normality criteria because the pattern of point distribution is around the diagonal line, the normality result can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Graph normal test

Source: Processed data

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test aims to analyze whether the regression model found a correlation between independent variables. (Ghozali, 2013). Multicollinearity can be detected in the regression model by looking at the value of tolerance and the value of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), with the basic reference as follows: “H0: There is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model. HA: There is multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression

model.” The criteria are as follows: If the tolerance value is greater than 10 percent and the VIF value is smaller than 10 then the H0 is rejected. If the tolerance value is lower than 10 percent and the VIF value is greater than 10, then H0 is accepted. The result shows that the tolerance value is 0.616 or greater than 10 percent and the VIF value is 1.622 lower than 10, it means that there is free from multicollinearity. These results can be seen in table 6 below.

Table 6: Multicollinearity test

Collinearity Statistics	
Tolerance	VIF
,616	1,622
,616	1,622

Source: Processed data

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test aims to analyze whether if the regression model is an unequal variance from the residuals of one observation to another, if the variance of the residuals of one observation to another is different than it is called heteroscedasticity. (Ghozali, 2013). If there are certain patterns, such as dots that form certain patterns (wavy, fused and then pinched) then heteroscedasticity occurs. If there is no clear pattern, and the points spread above and below zero on the Y axis then there is no heteroscedasticity. The results of the study show that the points spread above and below zero on the Y axis which conclude that no heteroscedasticity problems. These results can be seen in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Graph heteroscedasticity test
Source: Processed data

F Test

The F test is used to show the simultaneous effect of the independent variables on the input variables. Ghozali, (2013). The calculated F value obtained from the regression results will be compared with the F table value, as well as comparing the significance value of the regression results with the alpha value. H01: Service quality and innovation do not have a simultaneous influence on customer satisfaction. HA1: Service quality and innovation have a simultaneous influence on customer satisfaction. The criteria for acceptance and rejection of H0 are as follows: If $F_{\text{calculated}} > F_{\text{table}}$, HA1 is accepted. If $F_{\text{calculated}} \leq F_{\text{table}}$, H0 is rejected. The F calculated for service quality variable (X1) and Innovation variable (X2) is 26.550, which is greater than F table 2,70, and the significance value < 0.1 . It can be concluded that H01 is rejected and HA1 is accepted. These results can be seen in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Result from ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	36,062	2	18,031	26,550	,000 ^b
Residual	65,876	97	,679		
Total	101,938	99			

Source: Processed data

Service quality (X1) and innovation (X2) simultaneously influence customer satisfaction (Y), so EDTL continues to improve service quality because service quality is crucial in the service sector. It can be done by providing good service which will make customers feel satisfied with the service obtained. Even though EDTL customers are satisfied with the current service, it does not mean that EDTL will stop there, but EDTL have to innovate in order to facilitate the company in serving customers. Innovations that have been implemented such as the use of the MOCHA application greatly influence customer satisfaction because it facilitates the payment for electricity.

T Test

T Test is used to determine whether each independent variable individually or concurrently influence the dependent variable. The second hypothesis is H02: Service quality does not have a partial influence on customer satisfaction., and HA2: Service quality has a partial influence on customer satisfaction. The Tirth hypothesis is H03: Innovation does not have a partial influence

on customer satisfaction, and HA3: Innovation has a partial influence on customer satisfaction. The criteria for acceptance and rejection are: If the value of t calculated \leq t table, then H02 is rejected, and if the value of t calculated $>$ t table then HA2 is accepted. The result of service quality (X1) shows that the value of t calculated is 4.307 which is greater than the value of t table which is 1.28034 with a value of significance $000 < 0.1$, so it can be concluded that service quality has a partial influence on customer satisfaction. The results of innovation (X2) shows that the t calculated is 1.947 which is greater than the value of t table which is 1.28034, with a significance value of $0.054 < 0.1$, we conclude that innovation has a partial innovation on customer satisfaction. With those result, it can be concluded that H02 is rejected and HA2 is accepted, and also H03 is rejected and HA3 is accepted. T test results can be seen in the table below.

Table 8: Result from t test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1,101	,315		3,497	,001
1 X1_SERVICE_QUALITY	,461	,107	,448	4,307	,000
X2_INNOVATION	,208	,107	,202	1,947	,054

Source: Processed data

The Service quality provided by EDTL greatly influences the customer satisfaction, that's why EDTL always provides good service to customers and continues to make customers feel comfortable when using their services because it makes customers feel cared for by EDTL. EDTL also not only improves service quality but also continues to innovate and keep up with technological developments, so this result states that innovation influences customer satisfaction. And innovation made by the EDTL great helps customers in their purchase

VI- Conclusion and Suggestion

Based on the results of existing research, it can be concluded that:

- Customer assessment of service quality and innovation provided by EDTL in serving customers is good and in accordance with the wishes and expectations of the customer. Hence it can be concluded that the customer is satisfied with the service obtained.

- Service quality and Innovation provided by EDTL affect customer satisfaction, that's why EDTL continuously improves their service quality so that customers feel safe and comfortable with them. EDTL also continues to innovate and keep up with technological developments such as developing sales systems through smartphone applications.
- The Service quality provided by EDTL influences customer satisfaction. Therefore, EDTL always friendly when serving customers, this friendly attitude makes customers happy and satisfied with EDTL services.
- Innovations made by EDTL influences customer satisfaction. By developing service systems such as providing MOCHA applications, it has been becoming easier for customers to purchase electric. Communication channels such as Facebook's social media and hotlines make it easy for customers to get information distributed by EDTL

Suggestion

In order to help EDTL, some suggestions are recommended:

- The Service quality provided by EDTL is already good, but they should improve the service quality in the speed of solving problems because customer assessments state that EDTL is less than optimal in solving problems faced by customers.
- The innovations made by EDTL are good, but they should be more innovative, such as providing other applications to make it easier for customers to purchase electric tokens and also report problems related to electricity.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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